

Improving the Properties of the Tire Tread by Adding SiO₂ and Al₂O₃ to SBR Rubber

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Abstract

Particulate reinforced elastomer composite was prepared by adding reinforcing fillers Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ separately to the styrene butadiene rubber (SBR), at different loading levels (0, 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 pphr). Also many specific tests are performed on these composites. The effects of fillers type and their loading level on the mechanical and physical properties were studied.

The results showed that the mechanical properties except resilience increased with the addition of both types of reinforcing fillers and with the increase of the loading level of them. Silica fillers increased these properties more than alumina fillers. The largest value of ultimate tensile strength, modulus of elasticity at 100% elongation, and percentage of elongation at break were (67 MPa, 13MPa, and 172%) respectively for the SBR composite reinforced with 25 pphr of silica fillers. The minimum resilience was (65.59%) for the styrene butadiene rubber reinforced with 25 pphr of silica, also it has the largest values of hardness and minimum values of abrasion wear rate; which are (85 IRHD and 0.91 mm³/mm) respectively.

The physical properties are significantly affected by the variables, so that the liquids effect (swelling) was distinctively affected by the loading level of reinforcing fillers.

The thermal conductivity was also increased with the addition of the reinforcing fillers and with the increase of the loading level of reinforcing fillers. Alumina fillers increase the thermal conductivity more than silica fillers. The specific gravity for rubber composite was increased with the increase of loading level of reinforcing fillers.

Introduction

Elastomer (Rubber) is an amorphous polymer which shows very large strains when subjected to stress and which returns to its original dimensions when stress is removed. Components based on rubbery materials play a very important part in engineering processes and products. The most important application of rubber is in the transport sector with tires and related products which represent nearly (70%) of rubber production [1].

There are many researches that have been made to impart the elastomer performance in engineering components by enhancing the physical and mechanical properties.

Sombutosompop and **Bohan** 2004 [2], investigated the effect of untreated silica, precipitated silica (PSi) and fly ash silica (FASi) as fillers on the properties of natural rubber (NR) and styrene-butadiene rubber (SBR). It was found that the cure properties of NR reinforced with (PSi) increase at loading (30-75 pphr), but lower properties were obtained when NR was reinforced with (FASi) at the same loading. All properties of filled SBR were very similar to filled NR except in tensile and tear strength, so that NR was the best.

Yamshita and **Tanaka** 2007 [3], used styrene butadiene rubber SBR type (1500) with rice husk charcoal (0, 25, 50, 75 and 100 pphr) and silane coupling agent. They also prepared SBR composites reinforced with carbon black for comparison. It was concluded that breaking strength increased by three times than that of pure rubber with silane agent, but it was lower when there was no silane agent. This is because silane coupling agent helps constructing a bridge between the rubber molecules and SiO₂ included rice charcoal, but not more than tensile strength of rubber included carbon black which is (25 MPa) because the rise husk charcoal cannot be crushed below (50 nm) like carbon black by shearing force generate by mixing.

Waddell 2007 [4], studied the effect of carbon black type (N220, N330, N351, N355, N660 and HAF), rubber type and loading level of fillers, with using reinforcing silica in model side wall compound of tire. The used rubber was a blend of butadiene rubber; natural rubber and ethylene propylene diene monomer (BR/NR/EPDM) as a matrix with (0-18) pphr of silica, and (35-50) pphr of carbon black. It was found that the hysteresis of compounds containing carbon black (HAF) could be reduced by partial replacement of carbon black with precipitated silica. Improvements in compound properties were in tear strength, cut growth resistance, but reduction occurred in resilience.

Al-Hatimi 2007 [5], prepared (75) recipes of carbon black filled styrene butadiene rubber SBR blended with (NR, CR, BR and EPDM) separately and at different loading levels of SBR (10-60 pphr). The effect of carbon black type (N375, N330 and N339), on the properties of tire tread formulation (hardness, tensile strength, and modulus, elongation at break, abrasion resistance and specific gravity) was studied and compared with Babylon tire specifications. The best properties were at loading level for SBR/NR blend was (30/70 and 40/60 pphr) for three types of carbon black. The optimum loading level for SBR/BR blend was (20/80 – 50/50 pphr) and for three types of carbon black, for SBR/CR were (30/70 and 40/60 pphr) for three types of

carbon black, and for SBR/LPDM was (10/90 – 50/50 pphr) for carbon black type (N339 and N 330).

Al-Mas'udy 2008 [6], prepared styrene butadiene rubber SBR, butyl rubber IIR, rubber blends of (SBR/NR) and (IIR/BIIR) reinforced by five loading levels of carbon black type (N375) separately; in order to manufacture cheap rubber material to absorb vibration in generator sets and other engines. Resilience ratio, damping time, resistance to aging and swelling had been measured and compared with specifications of standard amounts. It was found that hysteric levels for (SBR) have been improved by the addition of carbon black up to (40 pphr) and a reduction of cost has been achieved by (72.17) % for SBR composite.

The aim of this work is to improve the recipe properties of tire tread by adding the reinforcing fillers (precipitated silica and alumina) separately in addition to the carbon black to elastomers styrene butadiene rubber SBR. These properties are: modulus of elasticity, ultimate tensile strength, elongation percentage at break, compression modulus, hardness: shore (A) and International Rubber Hardness Degree (IRHD), rebound resilience, abrasion wear resistance, thermal conductivity, swelling and specific gravity.

Experimental Work

The basic ingredients of recipe formulation used in this work are based on the basic formulation of passenger tire tread illustrated in table (1). Rubber processing technology consists of compounding, mixing, shaping; generally molding, and vulcanization. Mixing and mastication are conveniently done using two roll mills (Calender). Rubber is always compounded with additives: vulcanization chemicals, and usually fillers, antidegradants, oil or plasticizer. This is work based on standard practice ASTM D 3182 of rubber material, equipment and procedures for mixing.

The preparation process of rubber composite for application in tire tread and other applications of SBR requires many mechanical tests which simulate the conditions these parts will be subjected to such tension, compression, impact, wear ... etc. Other physical tests are also necessary such as effect of liquids, thermal conductivity...etc.

Mechanical characteristics are influenced by many variables such as process variable, type of primary and secondary interatomic bonds, stocking condition of product especially for polymers....etc. It is therefore necessary to investigate certain properties to predict rubber performance.

Table 1: Recipe Formulation of Present Work.

Item	Material	Loading level (pphr)
1	SBR	100
2	Zinc oxide (activator)	5
3	Stearic acid (activator)	2
4	Antioxidant	1.5
5	Antiozonant	1.5
6	Process oil	5
7	Carbon black (N339)	25
8	Precipitated silica	(0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25)
9	Alumina	(0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25)
10	Silane Coupling agent (PSAS)	----
11	Sulphur	5
12	Accelerator (TMTD)	1.7
13	Retarder (MBTS)	0.1
14	Reclaim	5

Tensile Stress-Strain

This test is executed according to ASTM D 412 for (24) different samples at 20 °C. The applied force is (500 N) with a pulling device velocity (20 mm/ min). The used tensile machine is (**INSTRON** 1195, made in England).

Hardness

This test is done by using two different measurements shore A and International Rubber Hardness Degree (IRHD) and according to ASTM D2240 and D1415 respectively. Five measurements of hardness were made at different positions on the specimens at least (6mm) apart to determine the average value.

Hardness is surface resistance to scratching, cutting, wear, indentation, and penetration. Material hardness generally depends on the type of interatomic or intermolecular bonds, surface condition, temperature, and others. There are two dependent measurements for rubber hardness which are: [7 and 8]

- 1- Shore (A) hardness.
- 2- International Rubber Hardness Degree (IRHD).

Abrasion Wear Resistance

Two-body abrasive wear tests were conducted on a pin-on-disk abrasive wear tester, designed for standard wear tests described in ASTM D 5963. In this method, the test specimen, which is (10mm*10mm*20mm), translates over the surface of an abrasive paper (SiC) with a particle size of (200 μm) mounted on a revolving disk. The test was done under the following conditions: period of testing (5 min), applied load (5 N).

This can be defined as the resistance to wearing away by rubbing or sliding surface of rubber against abrasives material that resulted in surface material removal. Pin-on-disk test was used, which depends on producing a relative motion between the rubber and an abradant. The based standard test in this work is that rubber cylindrical blocks are fixed in a vertical holder and pressed against a rotating abrasive paper disc at specific force, time, temperature, and velocity. To estimate the abrasion resistance, wear rate could be computed by using the following equation (1) [9, 10 and 11].

$$K_c = \frac{\Delta m}{\rho_c \cdot V_s \cdot t} = \frac{m_1 - m_2}{\rho_c \cdot V_s \cdot t} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where:-

- K_c** : Wear rate of composite (mm³/mm)
- Δm** : Mass loss (g) = **m₁** – **m₂**.
- m₁** : Weight of specimen before test (g).
- m₂** : Weight of specimen after test (g).
- ρ_c** : Density of specimen (g /mm³).
- V_s** : Sliding Speed (mm /s).
- t** : Sliding Time (s).

Resilience

Resilience is the ratio of the energy returned upon recovery from deformation to the impact energy required to produce the deformation of rubber component. Impact strength for other materials is the energy required for crack per cross sectional area, but in case of impacted rubber is different. The impact energy does not cause crack in rubber, and most of this energy is returned as a mechanical energy and the residue is dissipated as a heat in the rubber [6, and 10].

Rebound resilience is a dynamic test in which the test piece is subjected to one impact only. Most standard tests measure the rebound of a swinging pendulum from the piece. The specimens used in resilience test are (40 mm *5 mm) according to BS

903 by using the (**WALLACE DUNLOPE TRIPSOMETER**).Rebound pendulum test is based on measuring the rebound angle of a dropped mass which impacts a fixed rubber specimen, and then the resilience is given by [12].

$$R = \frac{1 - \text{Cos} (\text{angle of rebound})}{1 - \text{Cos} (\text{angle of fall})} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Effect of liquids

ASTM D 471 had been used to determine the mass change percentage of rubber material due to liquid absorption. This method involves cutting standard test specimens and weighted it in air. Then three specimens are immersed in a glass test tube [13]. One of them contains a liquid (engine oil type Fox Petan Super GT with a viscosity of 0.0003258 m²/sec) and the other contains (water) at room temperature. The immersing times were (22, 46, 72, 166, and 670 hr). The exposed specimens are brought to room temperature, dipped briefly in acetone, blotted dry with filter paper and weighted by 4-digits balance.

In this work, change in mass method is employed when immersed rubber specimens are under specific temperature and time. Calculation of this method is represented in equation (3).

$$\text{Change in Mass\%} = [(W_2 - W_1) / W_1] * 100 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where:-

W₁: mass of specimen before immersion (g).

W₂: Mass of specimen after Immersion (g).

Thermal Conductivity

Thermal conductivity test is carried out on test specimens, which is (40mm*4mm), by using the (Lee’s Disk). The power supply is determined at an electric current of (i = 0.2A) and an electric potential of (v = 6V) which re transformed into thermal energy through a coil heater. The period of test is over when T₁, T₂, and T₃ are in steady state.

Thermal conductivity is the ability of a material to transfer the thermal energy. This occurs when there is a thermal difference between two regions. Thermal conductivity coefficient can be given as:

$$Q = -k \frac{dT}{dx} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where:-

Q : Thermal flux is heat flow per unit time per unit sectional area in the flow direction (W/m²).

K : Thermal conductivity coefficient (W/m.°C).

$\frac{dT}{dx}$: Temperature differences through the system thickness (°C/m).

Lee disk is widely used to compute thermal conductivity different material. Coefficient of thermal conductivity could be calculated when electric is applied with specific voltage and current passing through an electric circuit which is connected with a heater. So the generated heat transfers from the heater to the brass disk (no.2) then to the specimen, and finally to the brass disk (no.1). When a steady state of energy is obtained, i.e. when input energy equals output energy as represented in equation (5), where T_1 , T_2 , and T_3 are recorded temperatures [14].

Input energy = Output energy

$$i \cdot v = \pi \cdot r^2 \cdot e \cdot (T_1 - T_3) + 2 \cdot \pi \cdot r \cdot e \cdot \left[d_1 \cdot T_1 + d_s \cdot \left(\frac{T_1 + T_2}{2} \right) + d_2 \cdot T_2 + d_3 \cdot T_3 \right] \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Where:-

- i : Electric current (A).
- v : Voltage (V).
- r : Radius of disk (m).
- e : Heat loss per unit time (sec.) through the cross sectional area (m^2) and temperature difference between the disc and environment.
- $d_1, d_2,$ and d_3 : Thickness of disks (m).
- d_s : Thickness of specimen (m).
- $T_1, T_2,$ and T_3 : The measured temperatures in disks no. 1, 2, and 3.

From above equation (7), the value of (e) obtained is applied in equation (6) to compute the coefficient of thermal conductivity (k).

$$k \frac{(T_2 - T_1)}{d} = e \cdot \left[T_1 + \frac{2}{r} \left(d_1 + \frac{d}{2} \right) T_1 + \frac{1}{r} d T_2 \right] \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

Specific Gravity

ASTM D 792 had been used for all density measurements, which are based on Archimedes base. The test specimen must be no more than (50g) in weight and no less than ($1cm^3$) in volume. In this test, a volume of each sample was ($12 cm^3$). Test specimens are weighted in air, and then immersed into water. The obtained values are applied in equation (7).

Density is the mass per unit volume of a material; whereas, specific gravity is a measurement of the ratio of mass of a given volume of material to the same volume of water at ($23^\circ C$). Determination of specific gravity yields for Archimedes base which states that the apparent loss in weight of a material immersed in a liquid equal to the weight of the liquid displaced. When the weight of the material and the weight of equal volume of water is known, therefore the specific gravity can be determined which is, by the definition, the ratio of weight of a given volume of material / weight of equal volume of water, as represented in equation (7) [15].

Specific gravity of material = weight of material in air / (weight of material in air – weight of body suspended in water) * Sp.Gr. of water \dots\dots\dots(7)

Results and Discussion

Tensile Test

Fig. (1) show the relationship between the tensile modulus and the loading level of the reinforcing fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 at 100% elongation for SBR composites. This figure shows that the tensile modulus increases with the increase of the loading level of the reinforcing fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 in a non-linear relationship at different rates. The SiO_2 reinforcing fillers improve the tensile modulus more than the Al_2O_3 reinforcing fillers. From this figure, the tensile modulus of SBR increased from 6.74 MPa at loading level (0 pphr) to 10 MPa and 13 MPa at loading level (25 pphr) for Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 respectively. This means that SiO_2 reinforcing fillers increase the tensile modulus more than Al_2O_3 fillers, this is due to the strengthening mechanism as follows *firstly*: large particle strengthening for Al_2O_3 reinforcing filler which has a particle size $\leq 30 \mu\text{m}$, this filler tends to restrain the movement of the matrix phase in the vicinity of each particle, whereas the matrix (rubber) transfers some of the applied load to the particles and bear fraction of it, and *secondly*: dispersion strengthening of SiO_2 reinforcing filler which has a particle size $\leq 40 \text{nm}$, this filler hinders or impedes slipping of rubber chains and requires high stress to bow them in narrow space among particles compared with large particles of Al_2O_3 and the matrix bears the major portion of the applied load [16].

Figure 1: Ultimate Tensile Strength vs. Loading Level of Reinforcing Fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 .

The relationship between the ultimate tensile strength and the loading level of the reinforcing fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 are shown in fig. (2) for SBR composite. From this figure, it can be seen that SiO_2 reinforcing fillers improve ultimate tensile strength more than Al_2O_3 reinforcing fillers because of the particle size and mechanical properties difference mentioned before so that the ultimate tensile strength of SBR reaches to 33 MPa and 67.35MPa at loading level 25 pphr for Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 respectively. The ultimate tensile strength of NR reaches to 36 MPa and 70 MPa at loading level 25 pphr for Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 respectively.

Figure 2: Tensile Modulus vs. Loading Level of Reinforcing Fillers Al₂O₃ and SiO₂.

Fig. (3) shows the relationship between the elongation percentage at break and the loading level of reinforcing fillers Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ for SBR. It could be observed from this figure that the elongation percentage at break increases with the increase of loading level of reinforcing fillers. This is due to the second role of filler, as well as reinforcement role, which is the voids filling that naturally exists in rubber structure, then they diminish these discontinuous regions which act as stress raiser therefore break strength and strain (elongation) increase [17]. The increasing percentages of SBR elongation from loading level (0 to 25 pphr) are 27.7% and 41.7% for Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ respectively. SiO₂ reinforcing fillers increase the elongation percentage at break more than Al₂O₃ reinforcing fillers because of the wider dispersion of SiO₂ which is greater than Al₂O₃ due to the finer particle size of SiO₂.

Figure 3: Elongation Percentage at Break vs. Loading Level of Reinforcing Fillers Al₂O₃ and SiO₂.

Hardness Test

Figure (4) shows IRHD plotted against the loading level of reinforcing fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 for SBR composites. Fig. (5) shows the shore (A) hardness plotted against the loading level of reinforcing fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 . From these figures it can be seen that rubber hardness shows significant increment with the increasing loading level of the reinforcing fillers in a non-linear behavior but at different rates in each Durometer tester.

It can also be seen that SiO_2 reinforcing fillers increase hardness at a rate higher than Al_2O_3 fillers. The SBR hardness reaches values of 79 IRHD and 85 IRHD i.e. the percentages of increase are 43.63% and 54.54% for reinforcing fillers at loading level 25 pphr of Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 respectively compared with 0 pphr loading level. This is due to the SiO_2 reinforcing fillers have a grain size finer than Al_2O_3 . This means that SiO_2 has larger surface area than Al_2O_3 fillers, which in contact with rubber mostly by physical bonds than Al_2O_3 . Composite with strong bonds made it harder by impeding the matrix motion along the stress direction. Also the same explanation is for (shore A).

Figure 4: Hardness (Shore A) vs. Loading Level of Reinforcing Fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 .

Figure 5: Hardness (IRHD) vs. Loading Level of Reinforcing Fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 .

Abrasion Wear Test

Fig. (6) shows the wear rate of SBR composite (as indicator of reciprocal of abrasion wear resistance) versus the loading level of reinforcing fillers respectively. This figure show that the wear rate of SBR is inversely proportional with the loading level of reinforcing fillers and the relationship is non-linear.

Wear resistance of unfilled rubber can generally be enhanced by introducing reinforcing filler into the matrix material. The explanation is that the sliding of abrasives on a solid surface result in volume removal, and wear mechanism depends

on the hardness of the composite component which is a key parameter in governing the amount of material removal, so that the presence of the hard reinforcing filler increases the effective hardness of the composite which acts to reduce the amount of material removal [18 and 19].

It is noted from these figures that the wear rate of SBR at 0 pphr equal $6.689 \text{ mm}^3/\text{mm}$, and it reaches to $2.96 \text{ mm}^3/\text{mm}$ and $0.91 \text{ mm}^3/\text{mm}$ at 25 pphr of reinforcing fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 respectively. This means that the rubber reinforced with SiO_2 fillers has decreased the wear rate (increase abrasion wear resistance) higher than Al_2O_3 fillers. This is because the reinforcement is decreased due to failure at the matrix-reinforcement interface or in the reinforcement itself. The abrasions wear resistance is influenced by the following factors **firstly**: interfacial properties where the SiO_2 filler has tougher interfacial bond with rubber by silane coupling agent than Al_2O_3 bonding. This makes the wear by interfacial debonding more difficult, **secondly**: geometrical properties where the particle size of SiO_2 fillers is finer than Al_2O_3 fillers; therefore it has a larger surface area than Al_2O_3 fillers. Fillers contribution to the abrasion wear resistance is inversely proportional to its particle size i.e. the finer particle size enhances the abrasion wear resistance by lowering wear rate. **Thirdly**: mechanical properties of the reinforcement i.e. SiO_2 ceramic is harder than Al_2O_3 in nature [20].

Figure 6: Wear Rate vs. Loading Level of Reinforcing Fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 .

Rebound Resilience Test

Fig. (7) shows the relationship between the resilience percentages against the loading level of reinforcing fillers of Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 for SBR composites. From these figure it can be found: **Firstly**: the resilience percentage is inversely proportional with the fillers loading level. This is because the reinforcing filler interferes with rubber chains and it impedes the mobility of flexible chains when they are subjected to stress. Also the interfered fillers could shorten the length of very long chains which leads to the

decrease of the rubber elasticity and then resilience. Therefore when the loading level of the reinforcing fillers is increased, its effect increases. **Secondly:** SiO₂ fillers reduce the resilience percentages more than Al₂O₃. This is due to the finer particle size of SiO₂ fillers more than Al₂O₃ which means a larger surface area and wide dispersion by which most of the impact energy can be absorbed and resilience is reduced. This is in agreement with the work [21 and 22].

Figure 7: Resilience % vs. Loading Level of Reinforcing Fillers Al₂O₃ and SiO₂.

Swelling (Effect of Liquids)

This test is performed on (22) specimens, half of which are immersed into engine oil and the others are immersed into water. Fig. (8) shows the relationship between the change in mass percentage *due to water absorption* and the loading level of reinforcing fillers Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ for SBR composites. Fig. (9) shows the relationship between the change in mass percentage *due to oil absorption* and the loading level of reinforcing fillers Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ for SBR composites. From these figures the following facts are observed **firstly:** the change in mass percentage is inversely proportional to the loading level of fillers due to the spaces and voids diminished by fillers. **Secondly:** water absorption is more than engine oil absorption that is due to the higher viscosity of oil compared with water. Also water swells through porosity of the rubber only, but engine oil swells by dissolving rubber and goes through, so that the change in the mass of SBR reinforced with 25 pphr of SiO₂ which was immersed in oil is 1.5% but which was immersed in water is 12%. **Thirdly:** The influence of fillers type on swelling is relatively small compared with the effect of the fillers amount. The effect of fillers type sometimes does not amount to much above the average error of measurement. However, there is a very pronounced decrease in matrix swelling when the filler loading is increased. These results are in agreement with the other workers [3].

Figure 8: Change in Mass % vs. Loading Level of Reinforcing Fillers Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ for SBR Immersed in Water.

Figure 9: Change in Mass % vs. Loading Level of Reinforcing Fillers Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ for SBR Immersed in Engine Oil.

Thermal Conductivity Test

Fig. (10) shows the relationship between the thermal conductivity and the loading level of the reinforcing fillers of SBR. This figure illustrate that the thermal conductivity is directly proportional to the loading level of the reinforcing filler depending on the rule of mixture, so that the thermal conductivity of composite is governed by its component amounts and their properties. Also Al₂O₃ fillers improve the thermal conductivity of rubber composite more than SiO₂ fillers. This is due to the thermal conductivity of Al₂O₃ which is greater than the thermal conductivity of SiO₂.

Figure 10: Thermal Conductivity vs. Loading Level of Reinforcing Fillers Al₂O₃ and SiO₂.

Specific Gravity

The relationship between specific gravity and the loading level of reinforcing fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 are shown in fig. (11) for SBR composites. From this figure the specific gravity shows a non-linear increment with the loading level of reinforcing fillers because of the voids filling by fillers. These fillers have high specific gravity than rubber, this makes rubber composite denser per unit volume. In addition to the above, the Al_2O_3 fillers provide higher increase to the specific gravity than SiO_2 fillers due to the higher specific gravity of Al_2O_3 .

Figure 11: Specific Gravity vs. Loading Level of Reinforcing Fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 .

Conclusions

The addition of the reinforcing fillers (Al_2O_3 and SiO_2) to the rubber (SBR) leads to improve the mechanical and physical properties. The conclusions are:

- (1) Ultimate tensile strength, modulus of elasticity, elongation percentages at break and compression modulus increases with the increase of the loading level of the reinforcing fillers Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 . The SiO_2 fillers improve the tensile properties of rubbers more than Al_2O_3 fillers.
- (2) The largest values of ultimate tensile strength, modulus of elasticity, elongation percentages at break and compression modulus were at 25 pphr of reinforcing fillers. So that for (SBR+25 pphr Al_2O_3) were (33 MPa, 9.98 MPa and 158 %) respectively. But for (SBR+25 pphr SiO_2) were (67 MPa, 13 MPa, 172 %) respectively.
- (3) Hardness of rubber composites increases with the loading level of reinforcing fillers and reaches a maximum value of (85 IRHD) and (85 Shore A) for SBR reinforced with 25 pphr SiO_2 . The SiO_2 fillers also improve the hardness more than Al_2O_3 fillers for both rubbers.
- (4) Abrasive wear rate is reduced by addition of (Al_2O_3 and SiO_2) fillers. SBR reinforced with 25 pphr SiO_2 fillers has the best abrasive wear resistance.

- (5) Resilience decreases with the addition of reinforcing fillers. The minimum resilience (maximum damping) character of SBR reinforced with (25 pphr) SiO₂ fillers was 65.59%. Also SiO₂ fillers decrease the resilience more than Al₂O₃ fillers.
- (6) There is a very pronounced decrease in rubber swelling with fillers addition and when the fillers loading level are increased.
- (7) Thermal conductivity of rubber increases with the addition of reinforcing fillers. Al₂O₃ fillers increase the thermal conductivity more than SiO₂ fillers. SBR reinforced with 25 pphr Al₂O₃ fillers have the maximum thermal conductivity.
- (8) Specific gravity of the rubbers increases with the increase of the loading level of the reinforcing fillers.

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